

Dimeric complexes of copper(II) with imino-oximes containing sulphur

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Abstract: Dimeric copper(II) complexes of some new ligands prepared from *N''*-(1*Z*,2*E*)-(hydroxyimino)-1-phenylpropylidene]thiocarbohydrazide (HTIPP) and benzaldehydes are reported in the present work with the objective of investigating the role of sulfur atom in coordination with the copper(II) ion. This objective was considered due to the expected ambidentate nature of the ligands. Six new ligands are reported herein using two electron withdrawing (-Cl, -NO₂) and two electron donating (-OH, -OCH₃) substituents benzaldehyde and HTIPP. The dimeric nature of the complexes was supported by molecular weight determinations by Rast method. Investigation of the magnetic properties and electronic and IR spectral studies along with powdered XRD studies was used to arrive at the suggested structure of the complexes.

Keywords: Dimeric Cu^{II} complexes, ESR, antiferromagnetism, distorted octahedral, Cu-Cu interaction, sulphur bridging, oxygen bridging.

Introduction

Transition metal Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes of the thiocarbohydrazide of isonitrosopropiophenone, abbreviated as HTIPP [IUPAC name: *N''*-(1*Z*,2*E*)-(hydroxyimino)-1-phenylpropylidene]thiocarbohydrazide] have been prepared and studied for their structure^{1,2}. All these complexes reveal that the sulfur atom does not take part in coordination, probably due to predominance of the thione tautomer over the thiol one.

It is premised that the thione-thiol tautomerism could be shifted to the thiol dominance so as to in-

volve sulfur atom in coordination with the metal ion. Hence in the present work we report the synthesis and characterization of a series of new ligands. The present study derived from HTIPP and benzaldehydes as per the general scheme shown (Scheme 1). Cu^{II} complexes with these ligands are synthesized and studied by various physico-chemical methods including powdered XRD studies.

Results and discussion

The elemental analysis indicates ML₂ formation of these complexes. The isolated solid complexes

Scheme 1. Synthesis of ligands.

are stable in air and their high decomposition temperatures ($> 200^\circ\text{C}$) indicate strong metal-ligand bond. The molar conductance data reports that the complexes of HIPTB¹-HIPTB³, HIPTB⁴ and HIPTB⁶ are 1:1 electrolytes while complexes of HIPTB⁵ and HIPTB⁷ are non-conducting.

Spectral studies:

The IR spectra of the ligands reveals the oximino, azomethine, $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$, $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ vibrations at the usual positions. A common feature of the IR spectral data (in the region $4500\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of all the complexes is absence of oximino -OH stretching vibrations revealing that the anion of the ligands occurs or forms by the deprotonation of the oximino group¹⁻³. Further indicating also the involvement of nitrogen and oxygen atom of this group in bonding with metal ion. On complexation the azomethine bands shift to lowering frequencies of up to 27 cm^{-1} indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen¹⁻⁶. Similarly the $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretching vibrations which are seen at 767 cm^{-1} in free ligands are found to be shifted by up to 19 cm^{-1} indicating participations of sulfur atom in the coordination⁷. Whereas in the complexes with ligand HIPTB⁴ to HIPTB⁷ the $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretching vibrations are not altered on complexation indicating non participation of sulfur atom in the coordination⁶. The metal-nitrogen and metal-oxygen bands appeared at $593\text{--}546\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $526\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively which are not observed in spectrum of the free ligand⁸.

The electronic data of all the Cu^{II} complexes in DMF solution show broad shoulder in the region $13245\text{--}14728\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 70.7\text{--}736.9$) and a peak around $16313\text{--}20877\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 108.7\text{--}6042.4$) to the transition ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}(v_2)$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g(v_3)$ respectively^{6,8-9}. Typical of a square planar rather than distorted octahedral geometry for the Cu^{II} ion. An interesting feature of the electronic spectra of these complexes is the appearance of bands that $24814\text{--}26385\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 4563.7\text{--}11144.8$) and $22173\text{--}23810\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 5053.4\text{--}12028.1$) observed only in complexes HIPTB¹ to HIPTB³. These bands in other Cu^{II} complexes with sulfur containing ligands have

been attributed to sulfur-to-copper $\text{S} \rightarrow \text{Cu}$ and nitrogen-to-copper $\text{N} \rightarrow \text{Cu}$ charge transfer respectively¹⁰. Hence in the present complexes, we are inclined to assign these bands to the transition suggested. It is noteworthy that the sulfur to copper charge transfer transition not observed in HIPTB⁴ to HIPTB⁷. Supporting the observation of sulfur coordination to the metal ion in the complexes HIPTB¹ to HIPTB³.

Magnetic measurement:

The Cu^{II} complexes of HIPTB¹ to HIPTB³ are diamagnetic while those of HIPTB⁴-HIPTB⁷ are paramagnetic. In which the spin-paramagnetism is quenched completely ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 0$) at room temperature. A sulfur bridged dimeric distorted octahedral structure is proposed since this may leads to antiferromagnetic interaction between two Cu^{II} centers of the dimers¹¹. While the magnetic moments of complexes of HIPTB⁴ to HIPTB⁷ is in range $0.85\text{--}1.90$ B.M. indicating of square planar Cu^{II} complexes¹². The low moments for the complex with HIPTB⁷ could be due to strong interactions between the neighbouring spins.

The EPR spectra of many dimeric Cu^{II} complexes especially in dimethyl sulfoxide solutions have been observed to break the dimeric form and yield the spectrum as if the complexes were monomeric. This could be because of the highly coordinating nature of the dimethyl sulfoxide solvent, which has one of the highest Gutmann donor number $D_s = 27$ and so is likely to break the bridge between the two copper centers of the dimeric species^{13,14}. The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0023$ suggests that the unpaired electron lies predominantly in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital, a characteristic of square planar geometry of complexes¹⁵. The G parameter falls in between 3.9 and 5.0 indicates the unit cell contains magnetically equivalent ions^{2,3}. Molecular orbital coefficient, α^2 in the range of 0.69 to 0.77 suggested the composite has been some covalent character and in-plane σ -bonding is more covalent than in-plane π -bonding. The β^2 (covalent in-plane, π -bonding) is in the range of 0.40 to 0.48 indicating no back donation is present in these com-

plexes. The exchange coupling constant ' J ' values of complexes of HIPTB⁴ to HIPTB⁷ are -9.95, -96.42, -8.74, -307.87 respectively suggested coupling types from weakly antiferromagnetic to strongly antiferromagnetic¹⁶.

Powder X-ray diffraction studies:

All the main peaks have been indexed by using appropriate methodology¹⁷⁻²⁰ and use of computer program (Winplotr). The 2θ values and relative intensities corresponding to the prominent peaks, unit cell parameters, crystal size, and density have been listed in Table 1. The unit cell lattice parameters a , b , c , α , β , γ and volume v belongs to orthorhombic system and space group is Pbnm. The complexes have the average crystal size of 1.6 to 1.9 nm suggesting nanocrystalline nature.

Experimental

Physical measurements:

The elemental analyses were carried by standard methods²¹. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Jasco FTIR 4600 spectrophotometer in the spectral range of 4500-500 cm^{-1} . Electronic spectra were measured on Equiptronic EQ-824 spectrophotometer in dimethyl formamide solution at KGKC, Karjat. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in dimethyl formamide (DMF) were obtained using an Equiptronic EQ-660 conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by employing Gouy's balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant at Institute of Science Mumbai. The effective magnetic moments were calculated after diamagnetic correction for ligand component using Pascal's constants. The powdered XRD pattern recorded in the 2θ range of 10 to 80° at a wavelength 1.5406 Å using Cu $K\alpha$ radiation source by MiniFlex II desktop X-ray diffractometer at Institute of Science Mumbai. The EPR spectra recorded in dimethyl sulfoxide solution at SAIF, IIT Mumbai.

Synthesis:

The Schiff base HTIPP was synthesized as des-

cribed in our previous paper^{1,2}. The Schiff base (HIPTB¹) derived from benzaldehyde and HTIPP was synthesized according to the procedure described earlier²².

Preparation of ligands:

Procedure outlined earlier for preparation of HIPTB¹:

Benzaldehyde (5.7 g, 0.054 M) in ethanol solution (25 cm^3) was added to an ethanol solution (75 cm^3) of HTIPP (10 g, 0.040 M) and 1 cm^3 conc. hydrochloric acid at 50°C and refluxed for 5 h, the resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized in hot ethanol.

Preparation of substituted benzaldehyde ligands HIPTB² to HIPTB⁷:

HIPTB² to HIPTB⁷ were prepared according to a similar procedure outlined earlier except instead of benzaldehyde, the substituted benzaldehyde such as 4-methoxybenzaldehyde, 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 2-chlorobenzaldehyde, 4-chlorobenzaldehyde, 3-nitrobenzaldehyde, 4-nitrobenzaldehyde was reacted with HTIPP.

Synthesis of metal complexes:

A general method was adopted for the synthesis of Cu^{II} complexes of HIPTB¹ to HIPTB⁷ was as follows:

An excess ethanol solution of two moles ligand was reacted with ethanol solution of one mole $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h, cooled, filtered, washed with ethanol and neutralized with excess hot water, dried and recrystallized to give a desired Cu^{II} complex.

Typical procedure for preparation of Cu^{II} complex of 4-methoxybenzaldehyde, $[\text{Cu}(\text{IPTB}^2)_2]_2\text{Cl}_2$:

An ethanol solution (10 cm^3) containing 0.615 g (0.0036 M) of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was treated with ethanol solution (50 cm^3) of 3.005 g (0.0081 M) ligand HIPTB². The reddish-brown precipitate obtained, was shake well for 10-15 min at room temperature and digest at refluxed temperature for 3 h. Further cooled

Table 1. Crystallographic data for Cu^{II} complexes

Molecular formula	[Cu(IPTB ¹) ₂ Cl ₂] (HIPTB ¹) ₂ Cl ₂ C ₆₈ H ₆₆ Cl ₂ Cu ₂ N ₂₀ O ₄ S ₄	[Cu(IPTB ²) ₂ Cl ₂] C ₇₂ H ₇₄ Cl ₂ Cu ₂ N ₂₀ O ₈ S ₄	[Cu(IPTB ³) ₂ Cl ₂] C ₆₈ H ₆₇ Cl ₂ Cu ₂ N ₂₀ O ₈ S ₄	[Cu(IPTB ⁴) ₂ Cl ₂] C ₆₈ H ₆₂ Cl ₆ Cu ₂ N ₂₀ O ₄ S ₄ Orthorhombic	[Cu(IPTB ⁵) ₂ Cl ₂] C ₆₈ H ₆₂ Cl ₄ Cu ₂ N ₂₀ O ₄ S ₄	[Cu(IPTB ⁶) ₂ Cl ₂] C ₆₈ H ₆₂ Cl ₂ Cu ₂ N ₂₄ O ₁₂ S ₄	[Cu(IPTB ⁷)Cl] ₂ C ₆₈ H ₆₂ Cl ₂ Cu ₂ N ₂₄ O ₁₂ S ₄
Crystal system							
Space group				Pbmn			
λ (Å)	1.5406	1.5406	1.5406	1.5406	1.5406	1.5406	1.5406
Unit cell dimensions							
a (Å)	7.6129	9.92248	4.56713	11.943	8.7108	9.3695	14.4206
b (Å)	7.5509	9.66458	4.60487	12.1767	8.8457	9.05079	14.2245
c (Å)	7.3448	10.36001	4.66814	11.3712	8.7572	9.8485	14.2577
A (Å)	0.01024	0.006026	0.02844	0.00416	0.00782	0.00675	0.00285
B (Å)	0.01041	0.006352	0.02798	0.004	0.00758	0.00724	0.00293
C (Å)	0.011	0.005528	0.02722	0.00459	0.00774	0.006118	0.00292
α (°)	90	90	90	90	90	90	90
β (°)	90	90	90	90	90	90	90
γ (°)	90	90	90	90	90	90	90
Unit cell volume, V (Å ³)	422.21	993.49	98.17	1653.65	674.76	835.16	2924.61
Density, d (g/cm ³)	12.219	5.594	54.747	3.396	7.974	6.892	1.968
Particle size (nm)	1.891	1.697	1.898	1.828	1.782	1.868	1.694
θ ranges (°)	20–60	15–71	33–80	12–80	17–79	16–80	10–69
Intensity (Arb. unit)	7–53	68–140.5	8–34	15–59	17–87	11–61	21–334

to room temperature, filtered, washed with ethanol and neutralized with excess hot water, dried at 110°C and re-crystallised from chloroform.

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References

1. R. G. Deshmukh, Dilip C. Sawant and Satish G. Pingle, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2008, **20**, 1723.
2. R. G. Deshmukh, Dilip C. Sawant and A. Venkatchallam, *E-J. Chem.*, 2009 **6(4)**, 993.
3. N. V. Thakkar and R. G. Deshmukh, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1994, **33A**, 224.
4. Abdalla M. Khedr and Hadi M. Marwani, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2012, **7**, 10074.
5. K. Shanker, R. Rohini, K. Shrivankumar, P. M. Reddy, Y. P. Ho and V. Ravinder, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86(2)**, 153.
6. N. J. Suryawanshi, G. B. Pethe, S. G. Bhadange and A. S. Aswar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2013, **90**, 1327.
7. Fatima Esmadi, Omar F. Khabour, Ala I. Albarqwai, Mohammad Ababneh and Mahmoud Al-Talib, *Jordan J. Chem.*, 2013, **8(1)**, 31.
8. N. V. Thakkar and S. Z. Bootwala, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1995, **34A**, 370.
9. Rajeev C. Chikate, Avadhoot R. Belapure, Subhash B. Padhye and Douglas X. West, *Polyhedron*, 2005, **24**, 889.
10. Jayendra Patole, Shreelekha Padhye and Subhash Padhye, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2004, **43A**, 1654.
11. Mohammad Akbar Ali, Aminul Huq Mirza and Ray J. Butcher, *Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 1037.
12. Om Prakash Gupta, *Int. J. Sci. Res.*, 2017, **6(2)**, 1365.
13. M. Jayarmudu and K. Hussain Reddy, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1999, **38A**, 1173.
14. Lenka Kuckova, Klaudia Jomova, Andrea Savorcova, Marian Valko, Peter Segel'a, Jan Moncol and Jozef Kozisek, *Molecules*, 2015, **20**, 2115.
15. G. Speie, J. Csihony, A. M. Whalen and C. G. Pie, *Inorg. Chem.*, **35**, 3519.
16. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, "Elements of Magnetochemistry", Affiliated East-West Pvt. Ltd., 1993.
17. V. D. Ingle, V. G. Shinde, A. S. Rajbjoh and S. T. Gaikwad, *Res. J. Chem. Sci.*, 2015, **5(8)**, 23.
18. Bipin Bihari Mahapatra, Ramani Ranjan Mishra and Ashish Kumar Sarangi. *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2016, **20**, 635.
19. Jai Devi, Nisha Batra and Rajesh Malhotra, *Asian J. Res. Chem.*, 2017, **10(5)**, 669.
20. N. Saxena, H. D. Juneja and K. N. Minshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 943.
21. G. H. Jeffery, J. Bassett, J. Mendham and R. C. Denney, "Vogel's Textbook of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 5th ed., 1989.
22. Dilip C. Sawant and R. G. Deshmukh, *J. Chem. Pharm. Res.*, 2011, **3(6)**, 464.

